

Study and Simulation of Seven Level - Ten Switch Inverter Topology

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Abstract. Compared to conventional two-level inverter, multilevel inverter performance is high because of their reduced harmonic distortion, less electromagnetic interference, reduced common mode voltage and higher dc link voltages. However complex pulse width modulation control, balancing of capacitor voltages & increased number of switches are main drawbacks of multilevel inverter. This paper focuses on study and simulation of single phase seven level inverter topology using only ten switches. This paper also presents two different control techniques for seven level-ten switch inverter topology. R-load is connected to inverter and simulation is performed using MATLAB/Simulink Software.

Keywords: Multilevel Inverter, Power electronics, SPWM Techniques.

1 Introduction

In recent research, there has been an extensive increase in interest to multilevel power conversion. The introduction of new inverter topologies & unique modulation techniques was involved in recent research studies. However, the most commonly used multi-level inverter topologies are multi-cell inverter [1], diode clamped inverter [2]-[5] and capacitor clamped inverter [6]. Some applications for these inverters include industrial drives, flexible ac transmission systems [7], traction applications in the transport industry and grid integration of non-conventional energy sources.

The seven level-ten switch topology is a symmetrical topology since the values of all voltage sources are the same. However, there are several asymmetrical topologies that need voltage sources of different values. This asymmetry results in the need of dc voltage sources having a specific relation between them and also the difference in rating of the semiconductor switches. This paper, presents study and simulation of a new multilevel inverter topology named reversing voltage (RV) [8]. This topology requires less number of components compared to conventional topologies. It is also more efficient since the inverter has a component which operates the switching power devices at line frequency. Therefore, there is no need for all switches to work in high frequency which leads to simpler and more reliable control of the inverter. Two different control techniques are used in this paper to drive the inverter. The simulation results of the seven level-ten switch inverter topology are presented.

2 Seven Level-Ten Switch Inverter

Output voltage is separated into two parts in this hybrid multilevel inverter topology. One part is named “level generator” and is responsible for level generation in positive polarity. High-frequency switches are required in this part to produce required levels. The other part is called “polarity generator” and is responsible for generating the polarity of the output voltage. Polarity generator operates at line frequency. This topology merges the two parts (low frequency & high frequency) to produce the multilevel voltage output. In order to generate a complete multilevel output, the positive levels are generated by the level generator (high-frequency part), and then, this part is fed to a polarity generator (full-bridge inverter), which will generate the required polarity for the output. This will reduce number of the semiconductor switches which were responsible to generate the output voltage levels in negative and positive polarities.

Fig. 1. Seven Level-Ten Switch Inverter or Reversing Voltage Topology

The number of possible switching states to control the inverter is four. The required output positive voltage levels produced by the level generator are as follows:

- 1) **Zero output level:** Switches S2, S4, S6 are ON which short circuits the input of the polarity generator results in the generation of zero voltage.
- 2) **One-third positive output level:** Switches S2, S4, S5 are ON, all other high frequency controlled switches are OFF results in the generation of $+V_{dc}/3$.
- 3) **Two-third positive output level:** Switches S2, S3 are ON, all other high frequency controlled switches are OFF results in the generation of $+2V_{dc}/3$.
- 4) **Maximum positive output level:** Switch S1 is ON, all other high frequency controlled switches are OFF results in the generation of $+V_{dc}$.

3 SPWM-A Control Technique

In order to produce seven levels by SPWM-A control technique, one reference sinusoidal and three triangular carrier signals are required. In this paper, SPWM-A is implemented for its simplicity. Carriers in this method have definite offset from each other and do not have any coincidence. They are also in phase with each other. The reference signal and three carriers for SPWM-A are shown in Fig. 3(a).

Fig. 2. Simulink model for SPWM-A Technique

Fig. 3(a)-3(g). Carrier/reference signal arrangement and pulses to switches of seven level ten switch inverter using SPWM-A Technique

4 SPWM-B Control Technique

In SPWM-B control technique, the reference signals have the same amplitude and same frequency equal to line frequency. They are in phase with each other with an offset value equal to the magnitude of the carrier signal. Three reference signals will be compared with the carrier signal to generate pulses for switches of inverter circuit.

Fig. 4. Simulink model for SPWM-B Technique

Fig. 5(a)-5(g). Carrier/reference signal arrangement and pulses to switches of seven level ten switch inverter using SPWM-B Technique

The modulation index for a inverter is defined as the ratio of amplitude of the reference signal to the amplitude of carrier signal. The modulation index for SPWM-B technique is redefined to be $M.I.=Ar/(3*Ac)$, where Ac is peak to peak value of carrier signal and Ar is peak to peak value of the reference signal.

5 Simulation Results

The seven level-ten switch inverter is simulated using 1000Hz carrier frequency, 50Hz reference frequency, Unity modulation index and value of each voltage source is 110V. Fig.6 (a)-6(d) shows output voltage waveforms of seven level-ten switch inverter using both SPWM-A and SPWM-B techniques.

Fig.6. (a) Output voltage waveform of level generator using SPWM-A technique. (b) Output voltage waveform of polarity generator using SPWM-A technique. (c) Output voltage waveform of level generator using SPWM-B technique. (d) Output voltage waveform of polarity generator using SPWM-B technique.

6 Conclusion

Seven level-ten switch inverter is simulated in MATLAB and Simulink software using both SPWM-A and SPWM-B techniques. This inverter topology has superior performance, offering improved output waveforms over conventional topology in terms of number of switches required, control system and reliability. In the mentioned topology, the switching operation is separated into high and low-frequency parts. This will add up to the efficiency of the converter as well as reducing the size and cost of the Inverter.

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